

Students' Perceptions of Language Etiquette Learning in Professional Contexts: A Qualitative Study

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ABSTRACT: This study explores students' perceptions of learning Language Etiquette in English for Professional Purposes courses in higher education. Using a qualitative descriptive approach, data were collected through semi-structured interviews, classroom observations, and students' reflective journals from vocational college students. The findings indicate that Language Etiquette learning enhances students' confidence, politeness, and ability to communicate appropriately in multicultural professional contexts. Role-play, case studies, and simulation activities were perceived as particularly effective; although some students struggled to apply etiquette principles in spontaneous or formal interactions. The study concludes that integrating Language Etiquette into English instruction strengthens students' pragmatic and intercultural competence and recommends the use of more contextualized and interactive learning activities to improve practical application.

Keywords: *Language etiquette, students' perceptions, intercultural communication, qualitative study, professional English*

INTRODUCTION

Culture has been defined in various ways by different scholars. Richenkova (2008:411) defines culture as “the qualitative characteristic that enables people to overcome their basic biological nature to give preference to their second nature, namely social nature,” thereby drawing a clear distinction and parallel between innate behavior and learned social behavior. Similarly, Thanasoulas (2001:10) emphasizes the role of heritage in shaping culture, stating that “culture is our social legacy as contrasted with our organic heredity. It regulates our lives at every turn.” These definitions highlight culture as a system of learned norms and values that guide human interaction. Within this framework, language etiquette emerges as an essential component of linguistic routines, which Agyekum (2005:1) describes as “the sequential organization beyond a sentence, either as activities performed by an individual or as interactions involving two or more participants.” Such routines are deeply embedded in everyday communication and play a crucial role in social interaction.

Consequently, when students begin learning a foreign language, they are typically introduced to language etiquette from the earliest stages of instruction, as communication commonly starts with routine expressions such as greetings, self-introductions, and other formulaic expressions. These routines constitute fundamental elements of a culture's etiquette system; however, their forms and usage may differ significantly between the learners' native language and the target language. Supporting this perspective, Dzameshi (2001, as cited in Anderson, 2006), in a study conducted in Ghana involving speakers of Ewe, a local language in West Africa, and English, demonstrated that politeness is perceived and applied differently across cultures, and that the factors requiring polite behavior are shaped by specific cultural norms and social expectations. Highlighted that the factors which necessitate polite behavior are not universal but are shaped by specific cultural norms and social expectations.

In higher education, especially in vocational and applied programs, courses focusing on communication skills have gradually expanded to include explicit instruction in etiquette-related behaviors. These involve strategies for showing respect, managing requests, responding politely, addressing superiors or clients, and adapting language to diverse cultural norms. However, despite the increasing recognition of its importance, students' perceptions of language etiquette learning remain underexplored. Understanding how learners interpret the relevance, usefulness, and challenges of this subject is necessary for designing more effective teaching approaches.

Previous studies on pragmatic competence and intercultural communication highlight the need for contextualized and experiential learning methods. Yet, little empirical research investigates how students themselves experience language etiquette learning in classroom settings, particularly in vocational colleges where practical communication skills are prioritized. Exploring learners' voices can reveal how they navigate etiquette concepts, how confident they feel applying them, and which classroom activities contribute most to their development.

Given this gap, the present study aims to examine students' perceptions of Language Etiquette learning within a professional English context. The study focuses on their understanding of its role in workplace preparation, the perceived benefits and challenges, and how learning experiences support their communication competence. By analyzing students' reflections, interactions, and classroom engagement, this research seeks to provide insights that can guide educators in refining instructional practices and strengthening the integration of etiquette training in professional English courses.

METHOD

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative descriptive research design to explore students' perceptions of Language Etiquette learning in professional communication contexts. The design was chosen to capture participants' experiences, attitudes, and interpretations in a naturalistic manner, allowing the researcher to describe the phenomenon based on the students' own voices and perspectives.

Participants

This study involved 43 first-semester vocational college students enrolled in the Language Etiquette course, which forms part of the English for Professional Purposes curriculum at a state polytechnic in Indonesia. The participants were drawn from the English for Business and Professional Communication study program and were approximately 18–21 years old. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select students who had completed key instructional modules and demonstrated active engagement in classroom activities, including role-plays, simulations, and guided discussions. The participants represented diverse levels of English proficiency typical of vocational higher education contexts.

Data Collection Techniques

Data were collected using three qualitative methods. First, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore students' perceptions, experiences, and challenges in learning Language Etiquette. Each interview lasted approximately 20–30 minutes and was audio-recorded with participants' consent. Second, classroom observations were carried out to capture students' interaction patterns, engagement, and communication behavior during etiquette-focused activities, particularly role-plays and simulations. Third, document analysis was conducted on students' reflective journals and selected course assignments to examine their understanding and application of language etiquette in professional communication contexts.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data were analyzed using thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework: familiarization with the data, initial coding, theme development, theme review, theme definition, and report writing. Interview transcripts, observation notes, and written reflections were coded manually. The analysis focused on identifying recurring themes related to the perceived usefulness of Language Etiquette instruction, challenges in applying etiquette principles, development of intercultural competence, and students' confidence in professional communication.

Trustworthiness of the Study

To ensure the trustworthiness of the findings, several strategies were applied. Triangulation was achieved by comparing data from interviews, observations, and documents. Member checking was conducted by sharing summaries of the findings with selected participants for confirmation. In addition, peer debriefing with fellow educators was used to enhance analytical rigor. Thick description was employed to provide clear and contextualized accounts of participants' experiences.

RESULTS

The analysis of interview data, classroom observations, and students' reflective journals revealed several recurring themes related to students' perceptions of Language Etiquette learning in professional contexts. Overall, participants expressed positive attitudes toward the course and emphasized its relevance to workplace communication. Nevertheless, they also reported challenges, particularly in applying etiquette principles during spontaneous or high-pressure interactions. The main findings are presented below.

1. Perceived Relevance to Professional Communication

Most students perceived Language Etiquette as highly relevant to their future professional lives. They acknowledged that learning polite expressions, appropriate tone, and formal communication strategies would support effective interaction with supervisors, clients, and colleagues. As one student stated in an interview, "This course helps me understand how to speak properly in interviews and formal meetings, not just in daily conversations." Similarly, a reflective journal entry noted that "knowing the right expressions makes me feel more prepared for real office situations."

2. Development of Confidence and Communication Awareness

Many participants reported increased confidence as a result of engaging in role-play and simulation activities. These tasks allowed them to practice greetings, making requests, apologizing, and responding to inquiries in professional contexts. One student reflected, "After practicing role-plays, I am not as afraid to speak formally in English anymore." Students also became more aware of how subtle linguistic choices, such as modal verbs, intonation, and honorific expressions, affect clarity and politeness. A journal reflection revealed that "small changes in words can make a big difference in sounding polite."

3. Improvement in Intercultural Sensitivity

Another prominent theme was the development of intercultural awareness. Students indicated that they became more sensitive to differences in politeness norms, workplace hierarchy, and email etiquette across cultures. Exposure to international case studies helped them recognize the need to adjust communication styles. One interviewee commented, “I realized that being polite in one culture may not be the same in another, so we need to be careful.”

4. Challenges in Applying Etiquette Spontaneously

Despite the perceived benefits, several students reported difficulties in consistently applying etiquette principles in spontaneous interactions. They described challenges in maintaining a formal tone, selecting appropriate expressions quickly, or avoiding overly direct language when feeling nervous. As one participant explained, “When I speak suddenly, I still use informal words without realizing it.” This concern was echoed in reflective journals, where students noted that switching between everyday language and professional English remained challenging.

5. Value of Interactive and Contextualized Activities

Students strongly valued interactive and context-based teaching methods. Activities such as mock office interactions, handling customer complaints, and meeting simulations were viewed as the most effective learning experiences. One student wrote, “Practice activities make it easier to remember how to speak politely than just listening to explanations.” Many participants suggested increasing the frequency of practice-based activities to further strengthen their communicative competence.

6. Positive Impact on Overall English Competence

Several students reported that learning Language Etiquette also contributed to the improvement of their overall English proficiency. They mentioned gains in vocabulary use, sentence structure, and pronunciation. A reflective journal entry stated that “learning polite expressions helps me

organize my sentences better and speak more clearly.” By emphasizing structured and polite communication, the course encouraged students to pay closer attention to linguistic accuracy and appropriateness.

This study explored students’ perceptions of Language Etiquette learning in professional contexts, and the findings reveal that students largely view the course as meaningful, practical, and relevant to their future workplace communication. These perceptions confirm the theoretical position that language etiquette is not merely a linguistic component but a socio-cultural practice embedded in professional interaction.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The strong perception of relevance expressed by the students supports Csajbok-Twerefou’s (2010) view that effective language learning must address pragmatic and socio-cultural competence alongside grammatical knowledge. Students in this study perceived Language Etiquette as directly applicable to professional situations such as interviews, meetings, and service encounters, suggesting that learners value instruction that prepares them for real communicative demands. This finding reinforces the idea that professional language education should prioritize functional and contextualized communication rather than isolated language forms.

Students’ increased confidence and heightened awareness of polite communication strategies further align with Thanasoulas’s (2001) argument that learning a foreign language inevitably involves learning a foreign culture. According to Thanasoulas, cultural norms and communicative conventions shape how language is used appropriately in social interaction. The students’ reflections indicate that their confidence grew as they became more aware of tone, formality, and linguistic choices, highlighting that etiquette learning contributes to both affective and cognitive aspects of language use.

In addition, students' perceptions of improved intercultural sensitivity support Csajbok-Twerefou's (2010) emphasis on the importance of intercultural competence in modern language education. Participants recognized that politeness norms, hierarchy, and professional expectations vary across cultures, and they perceived this awareness as essential for successful communication in global workplaces. This suggests that Language Etiquette instruction plays a crucial role in preparing students to navigate multicultural professional environments.

Despite these positive perceptions, students also acknowledged challenges in applying etiquette principles spontaneously, particularly in high-pressure or unplanned interactions. This perception resonates with Thanasoulas's (2001) observation that socio-cultural competence develops gradually and is influenced by learners' first-language norms. The difficulty reported by students indicates that while etiquette knowledge can be taught explicitly, its automatic use requires continuous exposure and repeated practice in authentic contexts.

Finally, students' strong preference for interactive and contextualized learning activities reflects their perception that practical experience is essential for mastering language etiquette. This finding supports Thanasoulas's (2001) recommendation that cultural instruction should be experiential rather than purely descriptive. From the students' perspective, role-plays and simulations provided meaningful opportunities to internalize etiquette norms, thereby strengthening their readiness for professional communication.

Overall, this study highlights that students perceive Language Etiquette learning as a valuable component of English for Professional Purposes. Their perceptions underscore the importance of integrating cultural awareness, ethical communication, and interactive practice to enhance pragmatic competence in professional contexts.

CONCLUSIONS

This study concludes that students perceive Language Etiquette learning as a meaningful and relevant component of professional communication development in English for Professional Purposes courses. The findings show that Language Etiquette enhances students' confidence, communication awareness, and intercultural sensitivity, particularly through interactive and contextualized learning activities. However, students still experience difficulty applying etiquette principles spontaneously in unplanned situations, indicating that pragmatic competence requires continuous practice. Overall, integrating Language Etiquette into professional English instruction is essential to bridge linguistic knowledge and appropriate workplace communication, and educators are encouraged to provide sustained, practice-based learning to support its effective application.

REFERENCES

- Agyekum, K. (2005): The pragmatics of request in Akan communication. *Legon Journal of Humanities*, 16, 1-26.
- Csajbok-Twerefou, I. (2010). Teaching culture in the EFL classroom: The role of socio-cultural competence. *Practice and Theory in Systems of Education*, 5(2), 153–160.
- Dzameshi, A. (2001). *A cross-cultural comparison of requesting behaviour in Ewe, British English, and Ghanaian English*. University of Reading.
- Richenkova, L. A. (2008). *Sotsiokul'turnaia kompetentnost' kak vazhnaia sostavliaiushchaia professional'noi kul'tury uchitelia inostrannykh iazykov* [Sociocultural competence as an important component of the professional culture of foreign language teachers]. In L. A. Milovanova (Ed.), *Aktual'nye problemy lingvodidaktiki i lingvistiki: Sushchnost', kontseptsii, perspektivy: Materialy mezhdunarodnoi nauchno-prakticheskoi konferentsii* (Vol. 1, *Aktual'nye problemy lingvodidaktiki*). Paradigma.
- Thanasoulas, D. (2001). The importance of teaching culture in the foreign language classroom. *Radical Pedagogy*, 3(3).